

Selectivity Coefficients of Sulphonic Acid Cation-exchange Resins in Sulphate Solution

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Selectivity coefficients of sulphonic acid cation-exchange resins for lithium-hydrogen, sodium-hydrogen, and potassium-hydrogen exchanges have been studied in sulphate solution (*ca.* 0.04*N*) at the room temperature (*ca.* 30°). The effect of mole fraction of counter ion in the resin and the relative degree of cross-linking of the resin on the selectivity coefficients has been investigated and the results have been discussed.

The cation-exchange equilibria of univalent cations with sulphonic acid cation-exchange resins in aqueous solution have been investigated by several workers^{1-19,21,22}. In most of these studies, chloride solutions were used and the postulated theories applied with varying success. In absence of any satisfactory method, yet available for accurately predicting the selectivity coefficients, it has been considered of interest to study the selectivity coefficients for sulphonic acid cation-exchange resins with univalent cations in aqueous sulphate solution.

This study includes the effect of the mole fraction, $\bar{X}_M$, of the counter ion in the resin phase and the relative degree of cross-linking, X (nominal %divinylbenzene content), of the resin and the average particle diameter, a (in mm), of the resin on the selectivity coefficients for lithium-hydrogen, sodium-hydrogen, and potassium-hydrogen exchanges in aqueous sulphate solution (*ca.* 0.04*N*) at the room temperature (*ca.* 30°).

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EXPERIMENTAL

Resins used were the sulphonated styrene-divinylbenzene copolymer type sulphonic acid cation-exchange resins of different X . These includes Dowex 50 resins (Dow Chemical Co.) of $X=1,2,4,8,12$, and 16 (these are further referred to as resins X1, X2, X4, X8, X12 and X16), prepared samples of similar resin (from Permutit Co., London) of $X=20$ (this is further referred to as resin X20) resins (Rohm and Haas Co.), Amberlite IR-120, Amberlite-200, and Amberlyst-15 (these are further referred to as resins IR-120, IR-200 and Am-15).

Lithium chloride, sodium chloride, potassium chloride, lithium sulphate, sodium sulphate, potassium sulphate, and sodium hydroxide used were of A. R. quality.

Moisture and Capacity of the Resins^{1,20}.—The resins were washed with distilled water, cycled thrice between NaCl and HCl, regenerated with a large excess of HCl, washed free of acid, filtered, air-dried, sieved, and stored in good containers. Several particles (*ca.* 50 to 60) of each resin were measured for the particle diameter with a travelling microscope and the average value was taken as the average particle diameter, a . The resin Am-15 was first soaked in methanol and then further treated as above.

For the estimation of the capacity of the resins, weighed samples (*ca.* 0.5 g.) of air-dried resins were contacted with 1*N* barium chloride solution (50 ml) in well-stoppered flasks with frequent shaking. After 2-3 days, the liberated acid was estimated by titration with a standard NaOH solution; the capacity was then calculated. Preliminary work had indicated that increase in contact time did not increase the amount of acid liberated. Table I records the obtained values.

TABLE I

Capacity of cation-exchange resins.

Resin.	a .	Moisture.	*Capacity.	Resin.	a .	Moisture.	*Capacity.
X1	0.215 mm	20.3%	5.24	IR-200	0.84 mm	29.8%	4.78
X2	0.215	20.4	5.20	"	0.58	28.1	4.78
X4	0.215	24.0	5.12	"	0.37	25.5	4.78
X8	0.215	27.0	5.09	"	0.23	26.1	4.78
X12	0.215	26.0	5.04				
X16	0.215	24.7	4.70	Am-15	1.13	25.9	4.58
X20	0.215	16.8	4.43	"	0.84	25.4	4.58
IR-120	0.580	30.8	4.96	"	0.58	26.7	4.58
"	0.370	29.9	4.96	"	0.37	29.5	4.58

*Expressed as m.eq./g. of oven-dried resin.

Solutions.—The solutions of salts were prepared by dissolving known weights in distilled water to known volumes; the solutions of sulphates were rechecked by sulphate estimation (as barium sulphate) and the lithium chloride solutions by titration against silver nitrate (standard) solution.

Determination of Selectivity Coefficients.—Weighed quantities of air-dry resins were contacted with known volumes of salt solutions (*ca.* 0.04*N*) in well-stoppered flasks with frequent shaking at the room temperature (*ca.* 30°). Preliminary work was carried out to find out the time, after which further exchange did not take place. After sufficient interval

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the solutions were analysed for the acid liberated by titration with a standard NaOH solution.

The selectivity coefficient, K_H^M , for the exchange reaction:

is given by

$$K_H^M = \frac{[\bar{H}^+]_i \{ [H^+]_e \}^2}{\{ [\bar{H}^+]_i - [H^+]_e \} \{ [M^+]_i - [H^+]_e \}}$$

where $[\bar{H}^+]_i$ denotes the g. equiv. of resin in hydrogen form added initially per litre of solution, $[M^+]_i$ denotes the initial concentration of cations M^+ in aqueous solution in g. equiv. per litre, and $[H^+]_e$ denotes the concentration of hydrogen ions in g. equiv. per litre in aqueous solution at equilibrium. By substituting the proper values, the selectivity coefficients were calculated.

Fig. 1, 2, and 3, respectively, show the variation of the selectivity coefficient for lithium-hydrogen, sodium-hydrogen, and potassium-hydrogen exchanges with $\bar{X}_M$ for resins of different X. Fig. 4 and 5 show for resins IR-120, IR-200, and Amberlyst-15 the variation of the selectivity coefficient with $\bar{X}_M$ in sulphate solutions for lithium-hydrogen, sodium-hydrogen, and potassium-hydrogen exchanges.

DISCUSSION

According to the complete Donnan theory, the selectivity coefficient, K_H^M , is given by

$$\ln K_H^M = \ln (\bar{\gamma}_M/\gamma_H) - \ln (\gamma_M/\gamma_H) + \pi(\bar{V}_H - \bar{V}_M)/RT \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where γ_M , γ_H denote the activity coefficients of alkali metal ions and hydrogen ions in solution, $\bar{\gamma}_M$ and $\bar{\gamma}_H$ denote the activity coefficients of alkali metal ions and hydrogen ions in the resin phase, π denotes the internal swelling pressure, and $\bar{V}_M$ and $\bar{V}_H$ denote the partial molar volume of alkali metal ions and hydrogen ions in the resin.

The change in the selectivity coefficient should therefore be considered to be due to the change in one or more of the three terms in equation(1).

Effect of Nonexchanging Ions.—The results obtained indicate that the selectivity coefficients for lithium-hydrogen, sodium-hydrogen, and potassium-hydrogen exchanges are higher, when the nonexchanging ion is sulphate, than when it is chloride (Fig. 1A, 1B, 2A, 2B, 3A, and 3B) and the order becomes $H < Li < Na < K$ in sulphate solutions. This is to be attributed to the changes in the first term of equation (1) and there may also be some contribution by changes in the second term of the equation owing to sorption of small quantities of electrolytes by the resin due to the Donnan-membrane effect.

Effect of $\bar{X}_M$.—Fig. 1B, 2B, and 3B indicate that in sulphate solution, the selectivity coefficients either decrease with increase in $\bar{X}_M$ or decrease with increase in $\bar{X}_M$ over some

FIG. 1A. Variation of selectivity coefficient for exchange with $\bar{X}_M$ in chloride soln.

- | | |
|------------|-------------|
| 1. $X = 1$ | 4. $X = 8$ |
| 2. $X = 2$ | 5. $X = 12$ |
| 3. $X = 4$ | 6. $X = 16$ |

FIG. 1B. Variation of selectivity coeff. for exchange with $\bar{X}_M$ in sulphate soln.

- | | |
|------------|-------------|
| 1. $X = 1$ | 4. $X = 8$ |
| 2. $X = 2$ | 5. $X = 12$ |
| 3. $X = 4$ | 6. $X = 16$ |

FIG. 2A. Variation of selectivity coefficient with $\bar{X}_M$ in chloride soln. for Na-H exchange.

- | | |
|------------|-------------|
| 1. $X = 1$ | 4. $X = 8$ |
| 2. $X = 2$ | 5. $X = 12$ |
| 3. $X = 4$ | 6. $X = 16$ |

FIG. 2B. Variation of selectivity coefficient with $\bar{X}_M$ in sulphate soln. for Na-H exchange.

- | | |
|------------|-------------|
| 1. $X = 1$ | 5. $X = 12$ |
| 2. $X = 2$ | 6. $X = 16$ |
| 3. $X = 4$ | 7. $X = 20$ |
| 4. $X = 8$ | |

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range and are practically constant over some range. For a resin of a particular type, this is to be attributed to the changes in the first two terms of equation (1). Small contributions

may also be attributed to some volume changes in the resin particle as $\bar{X}_M$ increases. Another contributory reason may be that the resin may be, to some extent, microheterogeneous²³.

FIG. 3A. Variation of selectivity coeff. with $\bar{X}_M$ in chloride soln. for K—H exchange.

- | | |
|------------|-------------|
| 1. $X = 1$ | 4. $X = 8$ |
| 2. $X = 2$ | 5. $X = 12$ |
| 3. $X = 4$ | 6. $X = 16$ |

FIG. 3B. Variation of the selectivity coeff. with $\bar{X}_M$ in sulphate soln. for K—H exchange.

- | | |
|------------|-------------|
| 1. $X = 1$ | 5. $X = 12$ |
| 2. $X = 2$ | 6. $X = 16$ |
| 3. $X = 4$ | 7. $X = 20$ |
| 4. $X = 8$ | |

Effect of X.—From Fig. 1B, 2B, and 3B the values of the selectivity coefficients were obtained for definite values of $\bar{X}_M$ for resins of different X. In Fig. 6, 7, and 8 the selectivity coefficients for lithium-hydrogen, sodium-hydrogen, and potassium-hydrogen exchanges are plotted against X for constant values of $\bar{X}_M$. With increase in X (Fig. 7 and 8) at constant $\bar{X}_M$, the selectivity coefficient first decreases as X increases from 1 to 2; then it increases, reaches a maximum, and again decreases as X increases. For lithium-hydrogen exchange, the pattern is rather different. These variations in selectivity coefficients with X, at constant $\bar{X}_M$, due to changes in the second and third terms of equation (1), are characteristic.

Table II records the values of the selectivity coefficients and X for maxima in Fig. 5 and 6. It has been observed that as $\bar{X}_M$ increases, the maximum selectivity coefficient is obtained with decreasing X.

23. Kitchener, "Ion-exchange Resins", Methuen, 1957.

Effect of 'a' and Structure.—For resins IR-120 and IR-200, selectivity coefficient was essentially independent of 'a' from 0.58 to 0.37 mm (Fig. 4 and 5). From Fig. 4 and 5, the values of the selectivity coefficients were obtained at different values of $\bar{X}_M$ and then from Fig. 6, 7, and 8, the values of X were read for lithium-hydrogen, sodium-hydrogen, and potassium-hydrogen exchanges. The values (Table III) indicate that X is fairly constant for IR-120. This is in agreement with the fact that the resin IR-120 is of the same type structurally, as resins X1 to X20 and of X about 8.

FIG. 4. Variation of selectivity coeff. with $\bar{X}_M$ in sulphate soln. with resin IR-120.

Particle size.

1. Li—H exchange: $\odot$ - $\odot$ 0.37 mm. 0.58 mm. Δ - Δ
 2. Na—H exchange: ,, 0.37 0.58
 3. K—H exchange: ,, 0.37 0.58

FIG. 5. Variation of selectivity coefficient with $\bar{X}_M$ in sulphate solution with resin IR-200.

1. Li—H exchange Δ - Δ - Δ 0.58 mm. 0.84 mm. δ - δ - δ
 2. Na—H exchange $\delta\delta\delta$ 0.37 ,, 0.58 Δ - Δ - Δ
 3. K—H exchange ,, 0.37 ,, 0.58 ,, ,,

And for resin Amberlyst-15.

- 1a. Li—H exchange $\delta\delta\delta$ 0.37 mm. 0.58 mm. $\odot$ - $\odot$ - $\odot$
 2a. Na—H exchange ,, 0.37 ,, 0.58 ,, ,,
 3a. K—H exchange ,, 0.37 ,, 0.58 ,, ,,

TABLE II

Values of the selectivity coefficients and X for maxima in the plots of Fig. 7 and 8.

$\bar{X}_M$.	K_H^{Na} .	X.	K_H^K .	X.
0.40	3.37	17.5	7.85	16.4
0.50	3.34	16.0	6.30	14.6
0.60	3.21	15.5	5.48	13.9
0.70	2.98	14.7	4.48	13.6
0.80	2.80	14.4	3.75	13.8

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For resins IR-200 and Amberlyst-15, it is observed (Table III) that for some values of the selectivity coefficients, there are no corresponding values of X from Fig. 6 to 8, whereas other values obtained for X vary significantly with $\bar{X}_M$. This means that the resins IR-200 and Amberlyst-15 are structurally of different type than other resins used though these are also based on styrene and divinylbenzene.

FIG. 6. Plot of the selectivity coeff. for Li—H exchange against X for constant values of $\bar{X}_M$.

FIG. 7. Plot of the selectivity coeff. for Na—H exchange against X for constant values of $\bar{X}_M$.

TABLE III

Values of X for resins IR-120, IR-200 and Am-15 from Fig. 4 to 8.

Resin IR-120.					
$\bar{X}_M$	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70	0.80
K_{H}^{Li}	1.40	1.35	1.36	1.38	1.40
X	..	8.0	8.0	8.0	8.0
K_{H}^{Na}	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50
X	7.8	8.0	8.2	8.2	8.4
K_{H}^{K}	4.20	3.93	3.67	3.40	3.15
X	8.2	8.2	8.3	8.1	8.0
IR-200.					
K_{H}^{Li}	1.55	1.50	1.45	1.40	1.35
X	3.4	4.0	5.5	7.0	12.0
K_{H}^{Na}	3.25	3.12	2.85	2.57	2.30

Table III (contd.)

IR-200.					
$\bar{X}$	12.0	11.0	10.0	8.8	6.5
K_H^K	8.65	7.95	4.32	3.60	2.85
X	..	..	10.2	8.9	6.2
Amberlyst-15.					
K_H^{Li}	1.42	1.40	1.38	1.36	1.35
X	7.0	6.5	7.4	13.2	12.0
K_H^{Na}	3.40	3.12	2.85	2.57	2.30
X	..	11.0	10.0	8.8	6.5
K_H^K	7.45	5.40	4.22	3.60	3.0
X	14.5	11.4	9.9	9.9	7.0

FIG. 8. Plot of selectivity coeff. for K-H exchange against X for constant values of $\bar{X}_M$.

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